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Research Article

**VISUAL RESULTS OF 27-GUAGE TRANS-CONJUNCTIVAL
SUTURELESS SURGICAL INTERVENTION IN DIABETIC
VITREOUS HEMORRHAGE**

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Abstract:

Objective: The purpose of this study is to assess the results of 17 trans-conjunctival surgical intervention and different complications and problem related to this procedure in the patients suffering from DVH (Diabetic Vitreous Hemorrhage).

Methodology: This research work carried out on 70 patients present with the not controllable Type-2 diabetes appearing with the DVH. The most important measured outcome was the BCVA (Best Corrected Visual Acuity). We also screened the complication after the surgery at every visit. We carried out the follow ups at one day, 30 days, 3 months and 6 months after the surgery.

Results: Out of 70 patients, 57.78% (n: 45) were male patients and 38.18% (n: 25) were female patients. The average age of the patients was 50.318 ± 4.578 years (93.0% CI: 53.130-55.570). For majority of the patients, there was improvement in the BCVA progressively with each succeeding visit of follow-up. BCVA before the surgery was 1.008 ± 0.204 Log-Mar in comparison with the BCVA at the very last visit of follow-up was 0.220 ± 0.229 . 4.88% (n: 8) patients developed recurring DVH in the duration of this research work, 2.58% (n: 6) developed the complication of cataract, 1.8% (n: 1) were present with the raised intra-ocular pressure and sub-conjunctival hemorrhage was available in 2.28% (n: 2) patients.

Conclusion: This particular type of surgery is very effectual type surgery without sutures with encouraging results regarding visual acuity, in the patients suffering from DVH. There are very complications associated with this procedure and the management of those complications is not much difficult.

KEY WORDS: Visual Acuity, Complication, Hemorrhage, Ophthalmic, Outcome, Surgical Intervention, Retinopathy, Diabetes.

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INTRODUCTION:

DM is the main issue of health in whole world now days that is the cause of many complications. This disease leads to the improper functioning of the persons in their very productive age. The patients suffering from DM normally develops ophthalmic abnormalities like cataract, distal neuropathies and glaucoma. The very frequent as well as blinding complication is the diabetic retinopathy. In USA, this disease of diabetic retinopathy is the main reason for blindness in the people having more than twenty-five years of age. The highest vision endangering problem is PDR (Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy) in addition with the DME (Diabetic Macular Edema). In our country Pakistan, the occurrence of PDR is from 2.448 to 3.0% patients in different research works. Pan retinal photo-coagulation was the main mode of therapy for the complication of PDR but current developments have encouraged the utilization of the instruments and techniques of surgery for various complications as the VH (Vitreous Hemorrhage) and TRD (Tractional Retinal Detachment) to be administered by the vitrectomy.

Par Plana Approach has revolutionized the surgeries of retina. Robert Machmer invented this machine for the very first time O'Malley & Heintz were the key holder for the invention of the three-port sclerotomy for illumination, cutting and infusion and dividing these, there was reduction in the size of the sclerotomy. MIVS (Micro-Incision Vitrectomy Surgery) has made the vitrectomy surgery very easy and there are many benefits of this procedure over conventional surgery method with 20-gauge like decreased time of surgery, high comfort of patient and lower conjunctival scarring. Glido Fujii in the year of 2002 initiated this procedure and introduced the instruments of 25-gauge. With the passage of time, deficiency in the flexibility of the instruments, adverse and low rate of flow became the most important concerns of this MIVS with 25-gauge. Eckhart appeared with a modern without sutures vitrectomy utilizing 23-gauge instruments in the year of 2003. In the year of 2010, Oshima introduced the 27-gauge MIVS with the incision size of 0.40 mm. This procedure decreased the danger of prolapsed of iris and permits the very fast healing of the wounds. Small size of wound of this procedure is the cause of the low inflammation and low pain after the surgery. This research work carried out to find out the outcome of visual acuity after 27-gauge MIVS for DVH and to evaluate the related complications.

METHODOLOGY:

The duration of this research work was from March 2017 to September 2018. This was a prospective

research work. The ethical committee of our institute gave the permission to conduct this research work. Non-probability method was in use for the selection of the patients. Already diagnosed patients of diabetic retinopathy were part of this research work. The patients present with any past history of ocular surgery, glaucoma, detachment of retina and cataract were not the part of this research work. We briefed the whole procedure of the surgery and purpose of the research to all the patients and we obtained the written consent from the patients. We collected the data in this research work as age of the patients, their sex, admission dates, dates of surgery and discharge from hospital and various complications after surgery. The evaluation after surgery included the investigating the vision acuity with the utilization of the Log-MAR chart, examination of the anterior segment, examination for cataract, calculation of IOP (Intra-ocular Pressure) with the help of Goldman's tonometer and dilated fundus examination with the usage of +90.0 diopter lens. We also considered the levels of fasting sugar, BP and HbA1c in the examination.

We used the standard equipment as prescribed by the inventor of the procedure. We carried complete vitrectomy followed by the PRP (Pan-retinal Photocoagulation) with the help of endo-laser. The tenure of the follow-ups visits after the surgery were at day one, after seven days, after 30 days, ninety days and last follow-up was after complete 6 months. A well skilled optometrist evaluated the BCVA with the utilization of the Log-MAR chart. We carried out the screening in the follow-up visits of the patients. We recorded and managed the complications in accordance with the prescribed methods. SPSS V. 21 was in use for the statistical analysis of thee collected information. P value of less than 0.008 was the significant one.

RESULTS:

Total 70 patients which underwent 27-Gauge MIVS were the part of this research work and we analyzed the data of these patients. The average age of the patients was 50.318 ± 4.68 years with a range from 40 to 60 years, of which 57.78% (n: 45) were the male patients and 38.18% (n: 25) were the female patients. BCVA level before the surgery was 1.008 ± 0.204 Log-MAR, which progressed gradually to 0.220 ± 0.229 at the very final visit for follow up. We carried out the comparison between BCVA before surgery and level of BCVA after one day, 30 days and 6 months of surgery during follow ups. We run the T test on all three pairs with 93.0% CI and displayed a P-value of less than 0.008 in every case. Statistical analysis of the level of BCVA before

surgery & at six months after surgery during follow up visit is present in Table-1.

Table-I: Paired Sample Test of Difference in Preoperative and Final BCVA

Difference in BCVA*	Mean $\pm$ SD	93% CI (Lower)	93% CI (Upper)	p-value
	0.575 $\pm$ 0.198	0.019	0.330	< 0.00

The complications after the surgery were managed after the surgeries are presented in Table-2. The patients present with the recurring DVH underwent another surgery after duration of few months.

Table-II: Complications Frequency Table

Complication	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Cataract	2.0	2.58
Increased IOP	1.0	1.8
Sub-conjunctival hemorrhage	2.0	2.28
Vitreous Hg	6.0	6.90
Total	13.0	

DISCUSSION:

Par-Plana vitrectomy is the choice method in the patients present with the not clearing VH. The efficiency of cutting of probes with small gauge vitrectomy probes has been increased with the recent machines of vitrectomy. The theory of the wounds of surgery based on the definition that much small much good. The surgeon from Japan totally shifted from system of 20.0-gauge to 25.0 gauge over with the modification of the good instruments as well as better machine for effectual vitrectomy. In the year of 2008, system of 27-gauge was in use for macular complication and simple VS & displayed both anatomical & vision outcome was much encouraging. This research work displays the significant improvement in the level of BCVA after 6 months of surgery. The most improvement was in the level of BCVA on the very first day after surgery and at the end of the one month after the surgery, whereas low level improvement continued up to 6 months after surgical intervention.

Oshima Y in his research work displayed the average BCVA alterations as 0.258 ± 0.308 . The system of 27-gauge not only simplifies the methods and lowers the time of surgery but it also mitigates the problems of wound sealing which are present with the machines of 23 & 25 gauge. Full spectrum of diseases of vitreo-retina can be easily cured with the recent instruments 27-gauge. A new tool for the bimanual vitrectomy is chandelier lighting system, which utilizes 25 & 27-gauge format or

endoillumination of a 29 gauge. Without suture vitrectomy has been stated to increase the occurrence of the hypo tony after surgery in this subject. Hypo tony was not present in any patient of this research work. A study conducted by Oshima Y displayed all the sclerotomies to have self-sealed with no hypo tony. Khan MA performed a research work which displayed 3.28% (n: 4) eyes with transient hypo tony, 6.38% (n: 6) eyes with transient ocular HTN (Hypertension) and 3.28% (n: 4) with VH as complications after the application of surgery.

CONCLUSION:

This surgery is very effective type of surgical intervention without sutures with very comfortable results in terms of visual acuity in the patients suffering from DVH. There are very few complications associated with this procedure. Those complications can be managed easily.

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